

Diacritic Reduction and Restoration in Serbo-Croatian (šišana / dešišavanje)

Research Data and Methods — preprint companion

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This document records the data, methods, measurements, and conclusions behind the study, and how the research was conducted, so that results can be understood, reused, and reproduced. It does **not** reproduce the raw resolution tables (tens of thousands of bald→accented rows); those are summarized statistically and are fully regenerable from the pipeline described in §3 and §12.

The restoration engine is released as the open-source, AI-free library **ioDiacritics** (MIT) — the software artifact of this study, referenced throughout at the pinned commit `be745a6` (2026-06-13): <https://github.com/ilya000/ioDiacritics/tree/be745a653605f6934ea127f1c2c909e242055b5d>, with runnable demos in <https://github.com/ilya000/ioDiacritics-Demos>. It is a small, deterministic, fully offline engine (dictionary + frequency prior + conservative guards; no server, no ML model, no user text leaving the device). The same library is also embedded by the author in two end-user macOS applications — **PolyType** (an adaptive keyboard / input aid) and **SlipWay** (a clipboard manager forked from **DrPaste**, <https://github.com/ilya000/DrPaste>) — through its stateless `str → str` contract.

Software availability and interests. The library, the evaluation harness, and the aggregate results are open-source (MIT) and the study is fully reproducible from open data; the library itself is not a commercial product. The only interest to declare is that the same author develops the two applications named above, which embed the library. This does not bear on the research: every reported number was produced by scripts on open data, none was taken from prior literature, and the validation corpora are independent of the dictionary source.

1. The phenomenon and the central framing

In computer-mediated Serbo-Croatian, writers routinely strip the Latin diacritics č ć š ž đ (dž) and type the ASCII forms — *šišana* (“shaved”) text; restoring them is *dešišavanje*. The orthography is a digraphia (Cyrillic and Latin in parallel use), and the shaved Latin register sits beside both.

The task is treated not as **error correction** but as **intent restoration**: the writer knew the correct form and dropped the marks because of the input environment, not out of ignorance. Three consequences govern every design and evaluation choice in this work:

- never touch a foreign-language token in code-switched text;
- never override the writing mode the user chose;
- the cost of a wrong edit greatly exceeds the cost of a miss — **precision-first**.

The task is defined at the level of the diasystem (the sr/hr/bs macro-language), not the individual language; a single engine, with per-variety data packs, serves all three. The framing is deliberately **operational and neutral**: ISO 639-3 hbs is used as a technical label, variety exclusions are made on computational criteria rather than on judgements of language status, and per-variety data packs and UI are kept separate. This matters because the status of Serbo-Croatian (“one macro-language with variants” vs. “separate languages”) is perceived differently across the region.

Scope boundary. Inside scope: Latin-script languages whose diacritics are stripped into ASCII (Bosnian/Croatian/Serbian; potentially Czech/Slovak/Polish/Slovenian, Romanian, Hungarian, Turkish with the locale ı/i case, German digraph expansion). Out of scope: cross-script romanizations (Arabizi, Greeklish, Cyrillic transliteration), which are many-to-many script changes — a different problem class. The hardest in-scope edge is Vietnamese (tone + vowel marks), where a dictionary-only approach is weak. The chief project risk is scope creep.

2. Task structure and the algorithm

The restorer is a dictionary-and-prior model with a hard gate. The full executable reference is a self-contained Python module (engine port + pipeline + evaluation + demo). The pieces below act as a semantic anchor; numbers in this section are Serbian unless noted.

2.1 Shaving (lossy char-map — the core operation). đ has two shaving variants because legacy encodings handled it differently: Type A đ-dj, Type B đ-d. Note that dž shaves through the ž branch as d+ž→dz, not through the đ branch; the capitalized form maps Đ-Dj (Type A) / Đ-D (Type B).

```
DIA = set('ććšžđ')
def shave(w, dj='dj'):
    m = {'č': 'c', 'ć': 'c', 'š': 's', 'ž': 'z', 'đ': dj}
    return ''.join(m.get(c, c) for c in w)
# Type A: đ-dj ; Type B: dj='d'
```

2.2 Reverse index with double-encoded đ (pre-resolves the dj/d segmentation ambiguity, so the runtime never has to guess how a given writer shaved đ). Proper-only forms (names) are kept in a separate set and never mixed into the index — a precision-first choice, since name/word collisions are a major false-edit source.

```
idx = defaultdict(set)
for w in common:
    idx[shave(w)].add(w)
    b = shave(w, 'd')
    if b != shave(w): idx[b].add(w)
# common = valid lowercase forms
# Type A (đ-dj)
# Type B (đ-d)
# proper-only forms go to a separate set, NOT into idx
```

The double encoding costs about 1.37× the number of keys, the price of removing a whole class of runtime ambiguity.

2.3 Lexicon expansion via spylls. The stock Hunspell unmunch silently drops affix classes carrying numeric flags — it loses high-frequency forms such as *bi*, *reka*, *smo*, *kaže* — giving 21.5% OOV on

the news corpus. Expanding SFX/PFX manually with spylls, including the cross-product (suffix-on-suffix and prefix-over-suffix), drops OOV to **2.26%**. The lesson generalizes: always verify expansion completeness against held-out text before trusting a lexicon’s coverage.

2.4 Document gate and classification (foreign gate, ≥ 2 witnesses). A “witness” is an ASCII token whose only restoration candidate is unambiguous and which is not itself a valid word and not in the foreign top-lists. Without the foreign gate, tokens such as *music*→*mušić*, *is*→*iš* enter the witness set and the classifier mislabels English text as shaved Serbian.

```
def doc_script(text, idx, common, proper, en=frozenset()):
    letters = [c for c in text if c.isalpha()]
    if not letters: return 'empty', 0
    cyr = sum(1 for c in letters if CYR_RE.match(c))
    if cyr/len(letters) > 0.5: return 'cyrillic', len(letters)
    toks = ALPHA.findall(text.lower())
    has_dia = any(set(t) & DIA for t in toks)
    witness = 0
    for t in toks:
        if set(t) & DIA: continue
        if t in en: continue # FOREIGN GATE
        if t in common or t in proper: continue
        cand = idx.get(t)
        if cand and len(cand) == 1: witness += 1
    if has_dia and witness < 2: return 'latin_full', len(toks)
    if witness >= 2 and not has_dia: return 'shishana', len(toks)
    if witness >= 1 and not has_dia: return 'shishana_weak', len(toks)
    if witness >= 2 and has_dia: return 'mixed', len(toks)
    return 'latin_plain', len(toks)
```

The six output classes (*cyrillic* / *latin_full* / *shishana* / *shishana_weak* / *mixed* / *latin_plain*) are used both as the product’s mode detector and as a measurement instrument in §5.

2.5 Ceiling B2 = mass of non-modal candidates (effective ambiguity). The structural ambiguous class is inflated by very rare forms (e.g. *da*→*đa*, 12.2M vs 169 occurrences). Counting ambiguous *types* therefore overstates difficulty. The right metric is the error mass a frequency prior loses if it always picks the modal reading:

```
total_mass = err_mass = 0
for k, cand in idx.items():
    masses = {w: freq.get(w, 0) for w in cand | {k} if w in words or w == k}
    m_total = sum(masses.values())
    if m_total == 0: continue
    modal = max(masses.values()) # prior always takes the modal form
    total_mass += m_total
    err_mass += m_total - modal
# B2 ceiling = err_mass / total_mass ≈ 0.4934% word error
```

2.6 Runtime restoration (logic).

```
restore(word, prev, next, isForeign):
    key = full_shave(word) # normalize dirty/partial shaving
    if word == canonical(key): return nil # don't touch correct text
    cand = idx[key]
    if cand is None: return nil # not in language → passthrough (gate)
    if not serbianContext and isForeign(word): return nil # binary foreign gate
    if key in cand and any(c has diacritic for c in cand): # ambiguous (sto/što)
        row = resolve_table[key] # Lever 1
        if row and (row.policy == 'G0' or (row.confidence >= 0.95 and row.winner != key)):
            if key in numeric_guard and neighbor_is_number(prev, next): return nil # "100 sto"
            return row.winner
    return nil # HOLD → passthrough
```

```

if len(diacritic_forms) == 1: return that_form      # deterministic
return most_frequent(diacritic_forms)             # frequency prior

```

The streaming variant (restore_text, live typing) guards only the **left** context, exactly as a keyboard sees it; the prepared-text variant (restore_prepared_text, whole buffer) guards left **and** right (lookahead). Both are pure str → str, with no network and no state — which is what lets the same engine sit inside an IME, a clipboard transform, and an offline library.

3. Data and dictionary construction

3.1 Corpora used (8 registers + gold).

Source	Type	Size
SETimes.SR 2.0	curated news (gold eval)	74K tokens / 3,891 sent.
OpenSubtitles frequency list (FrequencyWords)	subtitles, counts	283M tokens / 1.9M types
Hunspell sr-Latn → spylls unmunch	lexicon	2.36M common + 0.85M proper
redi.wikitweetweb.sr.tm (srWaC)	web lexicon / TM	1.62M keys
ReLDI-NormTagNER-sr 3.0	tweets, manual T/L tags	3,748 tweets
SentiComments.SR	film comments, orig/corr pairs (gold)	3,490
Forum <i>krstarica</i> (own crawl v1/v2)	general UGC	1,466 + 2,927
<i>benchmark.rs</i> (own crawl v2)	IT forum	2,998
YouTube live comments	comments	733 / 16 videos
EN / DE top-50K	gate dictionaries	2×50K

3.2 Collection method and lessons. A first crawler with a single shared target quota starved one site (one forum filled the quota before the other was reached); the fix was per-site quotas with deduplication on (source, raw_text). Published corpora are preferred over self-collected ones for reproducibility and ethics; self-collection is reserved for registers that do not otherwise exist (live forums, a 2026 cross-section). One source (Reddit) was abandoned after blanket request blocking, which is acceptable — published corpora are the stronger evidence anyway.

The YouTube extraction is itself a transferable method: from the page context, fetch the watch page, find the continuation token backward from the comment-section marker, POST to the comments endpoint, and read commentEntityPayload. Bulk transport out of the browser is done by chunked logging with visible delimiters (a direct return is truncated and URL-based transport is filtered). A two-pass exact-count method is used: the browser returns unique token types, those are classified against the full lexicon in the container, and a corpus-specific witness set is returned to the browser for an exact in-place count.

3.3 Reverse-index build — three robustness rules. 1. **Min-frequency (default ≥3-5).** Discards phantom OCR/typo diacritic forms (šmo@8, nišam@10, žbog@9) that would otherwise turn a safe ASCII word into a *falsely ambiguous* key. The filter removes about 86% of ambiguous keys (≈33k→≈2k) with no recall loss — genuine rare words occur dozens of times — and shrinks the dictionary (edit-error 0.59%→0.36%; 33MB→~5MB). 2. **Frequency.** When a count is available, rank candidates by count descending; the “most-frequent wins” prior is correct even on an alphabetically sorted source file. 3. **Case.** A form seen only capitalized is treated as a proper noun and dropped (precision-first; otherwise Mozes→mozes would block the frequent možeš). A key whose only candidate equals itself goes into a compact invariant set (needed only by the gate), not into the main index.

3.4 Per-language recipes. - **Croatian** — the raw frequency list (OpenSubtitles) contains both država and the bald drzava, which would poison the index, so it is filtered through a clean Hunspell

hr that keeps only validated words (drops *država*, keeps *sto/što*). Recall rises monotonically with lexicon size: 50k→11,338 keys/61.5%, full→76,116/79.6%, then up to 156,922. - **Serbian** — the only Hunspell sr is contaminated (it lists bald non-words such as *moze/rec* as valid stems), so it cannot be used as a filter. The source is instead a curated diacritic word list (*ekavica reč/veš/način* with srWaC frequencies). Two adjustments: bald valid homographs (*da, sto, kuca*) are injected as candidates so they are not over-restored, and an *ekavica* protect-list covers forms missing from the *ijekavica* Hunspell (fixing e.g. *gde-gđe*). - **Bosnian** — grown 11,350→114,092 keys via the full bs frequency list plus an hr-Hunspell filter.

Method insight. Diacritic-bearing forms need no Hunspell filter at all: because shaving *removes* diacritics, the presence of *č/ć/š/ž/đ* in a frequency list already proves the form is genuine. Only the diacritic-free homographs are run through Hunspell. The lossiness of shaving thus doubles as a free quality filter — a direct corollary of the “shaving is lossy” premise.

3.5 Resolve table (Lever 1). For each ambiguous key (one whose bald form is itself a candidate), a winner is chosen by an **independent** frequency prior — Leipzig wiki/news, deliberately *not* the OpenSubtitles source of the dictionary, to avoid contamination. $conf = \text{freq}(\text{accented}) / \Sigma \text{freq}(\text{candidates})$; the policy is GO if $conf \geq \theta$ (0.95), else HOLD. A compact bald-winner map plus a numeric guard is baked into the pack. The decontamination of the prior is critical: using the dictionary’s own source as the prior inflates confidence on exactly the homographs where it should be cautious.

4. Resolution table — statistics (raw rows not included)

The Serbian table has **29,682** keys with columns *rank · bald · winner · confidence · policy · numeric_guard · candidates*. At $\theta = 0.95$ it splits into **8,680 GO / 21,002 HOLD**. A scan of 351,994 sentences found that only **1,396** GO rules ever fire (3,754 never fire — a dead tail), so the shipped Serbian table is trimmed 5,150→1,396 with no recall change. The trim was measured, not guessed: of the 1,396 kept, 896 fire only rarely and a blind “top-500” cut would have discarded them.

Per-variety GO-rule counts after rebuilding all three through one builder at $\theta=0.95$ on a comparable Leipzig prior: **sr 1,396 · hr 578 · bs 481**. The asymmetry is a property of the source priors, not the languages: rebuilt cleanly, Serbian yields 497 GO rules (in the hr/bs band); the larger shipped Serbian count came from a much larger original prior, of which only ~4% had Leipzig-300K confirmation. The full tables are regenerable from the pipeline in §3 and the commands in §11.

5. Study 1 — how people actually write

5.1 Register gradient (token-level % shaved, foreign-gated).

Register	Cyrillic	Shaved
News (SETimes)	—	~0% (floor 0.08%)
Subtitles	3.35%	4.60%
Forum krstarica (general)	3.3%	14.8%
Forum krstarica (politics/daily)	5.8%	21.9%
Twitter (ReLDI)	n/a	32.1%
YouTube live (2026)	15.6% doc / 19.3% tok	38.8%
Film comments	0.75%	41.5%
benchmark.rs (IT forum)	2.1%	45.1% (max)

The IT forum — an educated, technical audience — shaves the most. Shaving is therefore driven by **register informality × the audience’s keyboard environment**, a two-factor model, not by low literacy. This directly contradicts a “carelessness/illiteracy” account.

5.2 Bimodality (within-document share of shaved tokens, documents with ≥ 3 evidence tokens).

Corpus	pole 0	core [0.2, 0.8]	pole 1
Twitter	66.8%	4.9%	27.2%
Film comments	57.0%	3.0%	38.9%
krstarica (general)	64.2%	9.4%	18.6%
krstarica (politics)	69.9%	3.8%	23.0%
benchmark.rs	45.1%	4.6%	46.7%

Across corpora **92-96%** of documents sit at the poles, versus **9.6-30.3%** expected under a binomial null model (benchmark.rs: 91.8% observed vs 9.6% null). Shaving is a discrete **mode** that a writer enters or not; carelessness would pile probability mass in the middle of the distribution.

5.3 Selective đ dropping. Among typed diacritics, đ accounts for 5.5%; among the omissions made by otherwise-complete writers it is **27-29%** (takode, međutim, između), and 28% of such posts drop **only** đ . That $\sim 5\times$ over-representation is a fossil of legacy encodings that lacked đ . A pure-šišana control gives 7.2-7.9%, confirming the effect is specific to near-complete writers.

5.4 Orthogonality to manual standardness. Cross-tabulating our shaving classes against ReLDI’s manual technical (T) and linguistic (L) standardness tags, shaved tweets split roughly 50/50 on both axes — diacritic omission is not what trained annotators flag as non-standard. (Caveat: that corpus is balanced 50/50 by design.)

5.5 Replication across a decade. Earlier manual coding (Ivković 2013) reported 71% / 56.5% de-diacritization on two news sites. Measuring 2014-2026 data over 8 registers with the same logic, shaving is stable across the decade — it is a norm, not a passing fad.

5.6 Measurement method (transferable core). (1) Unambiguous-pair method: witnesses are bald forms with a single restoration candidate, not matching a valid word and not in the foreign top-lists; the shaving rate is witnesses / (witnesses + typed-diacritic tokens), with a noise floor near 0.1%. (2) Decontamination: frequency lists are themselves infected by the phenomenon (the count of bald boze already includes shaved Bože), so the bald form’s count is corrected by subtracting the expected shaved mass of its partner, using the global shaving rate on unambiguous pairs (4.65% on subtitles). (3) The foreign gate is mandatory in the *measurement* tool, not only the product — without it music, is become the top “witnesses”. (4) Capitalization is a free signal: lowercasing creates spurious pairs (4,679 name collisions), so a separate proper-noun index handles Titlecase.

6. Study 2 — anatomy of the restoration task

6.1 Inventory (case-aware, common lexicon). 2,355,050 common forms + 851,071 proper-only. The three resolution classes: invariant (no diacritic possible) **1,421,138 = 59.8%**; deterministic (single candidate) **923,635 = 38.9%**; ambiguous **29,682 = 1.25% of types**. Token-weighted, the ambiguous class is **9.1%** (news) to **14.0%** (subtitles) — so about 87-91% of tokens resolve with a single lookup and no context. Segmentation traps: literal dj (as in *nadjačati*) appears in 10,214 forms vs đ in 73,973; literal dz (as in *nadzor*) in 1,890 vs dž in 26,972.

6.2 Ceiling and concentration. The dictionary + unigram ceiling is **0.4934% word error**. The residual is extremely concentrated: **50% of the error mass is in 13 forms, and 90% is in 397**. The “hard 1%” is therefore a closed, learnable set — the quantitative basis for the claim that an LLM is unnecessary at runtime for the measured residual.

6.3 Top true minimal pairs (error = the lost mass of the non-modal reading).

bald	error mass	candidates (frequency)
reci	195,914	reći 209,582 · reci 162,300 · reči 33,614
nas	88,679	nas 399,098 · naš 88,679
vas	87,674	vas 545,500 · vaš 87,674
sto	79,637	što 1,775,707 · sto 79,637
ce / će	56,769	će 847,670 · ce 56,769
gospodo	41,420	gospođo 43,521 · gospodo 41,420
ista	16,876	ista 16,991 · išta 16,876
vise	16,812	više 462,469 · vise 16,812
znaci	14,945	znači 205,163 · znaci 14,945
zao	11,651	žao 200,759 · zao 11,651

6.4 Baseline ladder (SETimes, 74,197 tokens; ambiguous 5,663 = 7.63%).

Baseline	word acc	ambiguous acc	precision	recall
B0 identity (do nothing)	83.82%	69.4%	100%	0%
B1 dict-only	96.43%	69.4%	99.35%	78.4%
B2 + unigram prior	98.54%	97.1%	98.52%	92.1%
B3 + bigram (5-fold CV)	98.65%	98.4%	98.95%	92.4%
redi TM-only (Ljubešić 2016)	99.66%	98.5%	99.01%	98.7%

Readings. B0 = 83.82% is the diacritic load of news Serbian — 16.2% of tokens carry a diacritic. The B1→B2 jump of **+27.7pp** on ambiguous tokens shows the frequency prior does the heavy lifting; the bigram adds only +1.3pp on top. The gap between B3 and redi is **entirely in recall** (92.4 vs 98.7), not in disambiguation accuracy, which means the bottleneck is lexicon coverage, not context modelling — a replication of the coverage-bound finding in Krstev et al. (2018).

7. Code-switching — a structural impossibility, and the gate

For a character- or dictionary-level restorer, the correct answer on a foreign collision word — passthrough — is **absent from the hypothesis space** unless a gate is added. Collision inventories quantify the exposure:

- **English top-50K:** 483 collisions; a gateless prior-based model is *forced* to corrupt **356** (is→iš, place→plače, nice→niče, music→mušić, case→čaše, use→uše, stand→štant).
- **German top-50K:** 358 collisions, **260** corruptions, including the articles das→daš, der→der, dem→dem, and los→loš, sah→šah. For the German-speaking diaspora this is the main scenario, not a corner case.
- redi without a gate corrupts 230 English words; it partly self-gates because srWaC contained some English.

In a controlled mixed-text evaluation (400 news sentences with English spans inserted), the gate raises English-span integrity **81.3 → 95.8%** at a cost of only **-0.59pp** Serbian accuracy; this trade-off curve is a paper figure. In the wild, the author’s own forums contain 972 mixed-language posts — **28.3%** of the IT corpus — which a gateless model corrupts in 166 places (core→core ×87, price→priče ×14, music→mušić ×7, case→čaše, basic→basić), reduced to **0** with the foreign gate. The cost of the gate is tiny (a few Serbian words like rec, ce that an anchor gate returns). A useful by-product: the top-100 corrupted words form a ready-made do-not-touch list for the runtime’s isForeign check.

8. The symmetric experiment (main result)

The apparent cross-language gap (Serbian 93.7% vs Croatian 79.6%) turned out to be an **artifact** of resolve-table presence and dictionary size — **not** of language, genre, or algorithm. With the engine fixed, the three varieties are statistically indistinguishable. All numbers use `seed=12345` and a **document-level (cluster) bootstrap**, $B=2000$: tokens within a document are correlated (one author, register, habit), so confidence intervals are computed over documents, not over words. Validation corpora are independent of the dictionary source, and no number was tuned to a target.

The shipped artifact totals **427,945 reverse-index keys** across three packs (bs 114,092; hr 156,922, built to 171,938 then frequency-trimmed; sr 156,931) and **2,455 confident resolve rules** (bs 481, hr 578, sr 1,396). The reliability passports cover **10,562 documents/posts and 21,185 fixable word instances**; the balanced register \times language matrix below covers a further **11,310 documents and 30,573 fixable word instances** under one comparable protocol.

8.1 Initial symmetric grid (genre \times language, resolve OFF, one engine). sr·Wikipedia 84.1% [82.9, 85.3]; sr·forum 81.9% [80.4, 83.5]; hr·Wikipedia 82.6% [81.3, 83.9]; hr·forum 80.0% [76.5, 83.3]; edit-precision 99.2–99.9%. The large apparent sr-hr gap collapses to overlapping intervals once the engine and register are held fixed.

8.2 Register \times language matrix (resolve OFF, size-aligned dictionaries; recall, 95% CI, edit-precision).

	wiki	news	tatoeba
sr (156,931 keys)	84.1 [82.9, 85.3] · ep 99.8%	82.2 [81.1, 83.3] · ep 99.4%	86.7 [84.6, 88.7] · ep 99.9%
hr (156,922)	87.4 [86.2, 88.5] · ep 100%	89.4 [88.5, 90.3] · ep 99.9%	86.6 [84.7, 88.5] · ep 100%
bs (114,092)	86.9 [85.7, 87.9] · ep 100%	88.0 [87.0, 89.0] · ep 99.8%	86.0 [83.9, 87.9] · ep 100%

All three varieties converge to a **~84–89%** band on every register, with overlapping intervals. **The driver is dictionary coverage, not language.**

8.3 Recall = f(coverage), proven by a curve on two languages (engine unchanged): bs-wiki 11k \rightarrow 60.4%, 54k \rightarrow 79.1%, 114k \rightarrow 86.9%; hr-wiki 78k \rightarrow 82.6%, 157k \rightarrow 87.4%. Monotonic growth is the signature of a coverage limit, not an algorithmic one — the strongest single argument that the gap was coverage.

8.4 Resolve lever (OFF \rightarrow ON), symmetric across varieties.

	resolve OFF (chat / Tatoeba)	resolve ON	Δ
Serbian	81.9 [80.4, 83.5] / 86.7	91.4 [90.4, 92.5] / 95.2	+8.5–9.5pp (CIs disjoint)
Croatian	80.0 [76.5, 83.3] / 86.6	89.5 [86.9, 92.1] / 96.4	+9.5–9.8pp
Bosnian	86.0	95.2	+9.2pp

Edit-precision does not move (the lever fires only on bald input, so its precision cost is zero). The gain is concentrated in a few hundred high-frequency head rules: a top-K ablation on sr·Tatoeba saturates by \sim 500 rules (500 \rightarrow 5,150 adds +0.0pp), which is what justified trimming the Serbian tail (§4).

8.5 Real-error track (SentiComments.SR orig/corr). Synthetic shaving could overstate validity, since it omits real typos and dialect. A parallel orig/corr gold set isolates the diacritic signal by keeping only token-skeleton-matched comments: 3,490 \rightarrow 2,619 skeleton-aligned \rightarrow 1,022 with ≥ 1 target \rightarrow **2,804 real targets**. **Real recall = 93.9% [92.9, 94.7]**, edit-precision 99.9%; resolve

OFF = 82.8% (Lever-1 adds +11.1pp on real data). The headline: real recall (93.9%) \approx synthetic (\sim 93.7%), so synthetic ablation does **not** overstate validity for Serbian — a strong methodological result that licenses synthetic evaluation for the other varieties. At the document level on the same gold set (7.20% of tokens actually shaved), word accuracy is 99.58% for B2 (recall 95.9 / precision 97.9), 99.30% for B2 + foreign gate (recall 91.5 / **precision 98.4**), and 99.78% for redi (recall 98.8) — the precision-first configuration trades a little recall for the highest precision, as intended.

8.6 Named baselines (sr-chat).

baseline	recall [95% CI]	edit-precision
do-nothing	0.0%	100.0%
naive most-frequent (no holdout)	85.0 [83.5, 86.4]	89.5% (381 wrong edits)
ours, no-resolve (precision-first holdout)	81.9 [80.4, 83.5]	99.7%
ours, + resolve	91.4 [90.4, 92.5]	99.6%

The naive lexical baseline buys recall at \sim 10pp of precision (381 wrong edits on homographs). A holdout restores precision ($-$ 3pp recall); the resolve table then returns recall (+9.5pp) at no precision cost. Our design dominates the naive baseline on **both** axes.

8.7 Bosnian / Montenegrin. Bosnian on clean Tatoeba: 79.4 [77.3, 81.7], edit-precision 100% (0 wrong edits on 1,332 fixable — a tight upper bound); on klix.ba UGC 91.6 [89.4, 93.7]. Montenegrin \acute{s}/\acute{z} : typed \acute{s}/\acute{z} pass through 100% (22/22; the letters are not in the strip map, so the key is non-ASCII and restore returns nil). Shaved \acute{s}/\acute{z} show no \acute{s}/\acute{z} -specific failures, only the pre-existing shared homograph tail also present in plain Serbian. The “zero code” hypothesis (Montenegrin is computationally near-identical to Serbian) holds, but “zero code” \neq “zero risk” — supporting an operational exclusion of Montenegrin from scope.

8.8 Independent audit. All 9 matrix cells were independently reproduced by an external code audit, which found and fixed two evaluation-harness bugs (an OOV key not lowercased, inflating OOV; the numeric guard not firing because the tokenizer skipped digits). Headline recall was unchanged after both fixes.

9. The research \leftrightarrow implementation loop

The honest denominator for recall is **fixable words** — ground truth produced by taking accented text, shaving it, then restoring — not all words. On a 6,005-post two-forum corpus (14,341 fixable words), the production trajectory below shows how each lever was found and why it mattered.

step	recall	wrong	what it taught
engine, honest denominator	73.5%	0.21%	gap = 12.7pp ambiguous-in-passthrough + 13.6pp OOV
+ dictionary 45k \rightarrow 100k	78.9%	0.25%	+5.4pp for 2.3 \times size; Zipf makes coverage expensive
their bigrams (80/20) on the bucket	93.2% bucket	—	left-only suffices (left+right = 92.9%, worse)
decontaminated unigram prior on the bucket	95.4% bucket	—	a static prior beats a low-data bigram, at zero runtime cost

step	recall	wrong	what it taught
+ resolve table v1 (rank-HOLD)	80.2%	0.26%	only +1.3pp — error mass \neq traffic mass
+ confidence policy (conf \geq 0.95)	90.0%	0.31%	+9.8pp recall for +0.05pp wrong
+ cap-250k dictionary	93.2%	—	shipped operating point
+ minfreq=3 (4.9MB)	93.7%	0.36%	size/quality knee
full flat lexicon	95.1%	—	research ceiling (~196MB RAM, undeployable)

Minfreq sweep (sr): 1→808k keys/25MB/94.1%/0.38%; 2→180k/5.6MB/93.8%/0.37%; 3→157k/4.9MB/93.7%/0.36%; 4→131k/4.0MB/93.5%/0.36%. The 1→2 step cuts size 4.5× for −0.3pp recall.

Capacity / RAM curve: cap-100k 40k keys/1.5MB/90.0%; cap-250k 108k/3.5MB/~15–20MB RAM/93.2% (shipped); cap-500k 237k/7MB/94.3%; full _{1M/33MB} 196MB RAM/95.1%.

Left vs right context (held-out 80/20, the sto/što bucket): baseline 0% → left context 93.2% → left+right 92.9%. Right context does not help; left context and the unigram prior are **substitutes, not complements**, so the runtime needs no deferred right-context parse and produces no lag or flicker.

Engine review (five defects found and fixed in the original implementation), worth recording as failure modes: (1) invariant keys were discarded, making the language check falsely negative — fixed with a compact invariant set; (2) lowercasing without a proper-noun branch let a name borrow a common word’s rank — fixed with a lowercase-only index; (3) building from a word list ignored frequencies, breaking the prior on an unsorted file — fixed; (4) JSON + dictionary lookup needs a DAWG/mmap for the full lexicon; (5) mixed-case input should pass through.

Deployment-target rationale (stopping arithmetic). With ~3 fixable words per message, 90% recall means a miss roughly every one or two messages; ~98% means a miss about every 15 (“always works”); the step from 98% to 99.5% is imperceptible to a user. The deployment target is therefore ~98% via a web-scale lexicon, then stop — a concrete instance of capability \neq deployability.

10. Conclusions and methodological lessons

Four cross-cutting results. 1. **Coverage \neq quality.** Accuracy is bounded by the quality of the dictionary *tail*, not its size; naive growth imports noise faster than signal (87% of the full lexicon is freq<5 noise). 2. **Error mass \neq traffic mass.** A rank-based HOLD adds +1.3pp; a confidence-based HOLD adds +9.8pp. Error is concentrated in a few high-frequency forms, so guards must be keyed to confidence, not rank. 3. **Capability \neq deployability.** The 95.1% research ceiling costs ~196MB RAM and is not shippable; the operating point is a deployment parameter, not a fixed property of the method. 4. **Left context and the unigram prior are substitutes, not complements.** Right context is unnecessary; the runtime needs no deferred parse.

Methodology lessons. 1. Run a verification search before every “first” — prior art (Ivković) nearly turned a claimed novelty into a desk reject. 2. The denominator decides everything — “9% recall” of all words vs “73.5%” of fixable words describe the same system. 3. Compare against a strong baseline, not against zero (bigrams vs passthrough). 4. Error mass \neq traffic mass: confidence guards, not rank guards. 5. Frequency data about a shaving phenomenon is itself infected by shaving — decontaminate. 6. Never transcribe data “from memory” — an incident with a hand-built witness set nearly corrupted an experiment with invalid witnesses. 7. The gate belongs in the measurement instrument as well as in the product. 8. Prefer published corpora (reproducibility, ethics); self-collect only what does not otherwise exist. 9. Move bulk data out of a browser in delimited chunks. 10. Coverage \neq quality — precision is bounded by tail quality, not size. 11. A

static prior beats a low-data bigram at zero runtime cost. 12. Left-only sufficiency — right context does not help. 13. Control confounds (register, dictionary size) *before* attributing a gap to language or algorithm — the core of the symmetric experiment. 14. Measure, don't assume — including about why two numbers differ (a “stale counts” premise turned out to be a property of the corpus, not the run). 15. Shaving's lossiness is a free quality filter: the presence of a diacritic proves a form genuine, so only diacritic-free homographs need Hunspell validation.

A note on figures. Results fall into four blocks that sit on **different axes** and must never share one: (A) the controlled cross-language matrix (recall by register, three varieties, resolve OFF, CIs); (B) the resolve lever (OFF→ON slope per variety, +Δpp, precision held); (C) coverage trajectories (recall vs log dictionary size, monotonic); (D) per-pack deployment recall, each measured on its own register. In particular, block-D numbers are different registers and are **not** comparable across languages — they must not be charted next to the block-A comparison. Figures should use colour-blind- and greyscale-safe palettes with variety colours consistent across panels.

11. Research framing, contributions, and planned validation

Central thesis. Diacritic reduction (*šišana* and its analogues) is an infrastructure-induced property of the writing environment, shared across a language family; its inversion is a computationally tractable, on-device task best defined at the level of the diasystem rather than the individual language. The work contributes along three dimensions: **sociolinguistic** (what the phenomenon is, and its register structure — §5), **computational** (the structure of the task, its ceiling, and what breaks naive methods — §6–§8), and **typological/systemic** (generalization across the macro-language, and a working privacy-preserving system — §8–§9).

Design implications and their evidence status. The study yields several design implications whose support differs in kind, and the distinction is stated explicitly rather than over-claimed: - *Treat shaving as an intent register, not an error* — definitional / by construction (§1). - *Shaving is a mode the writer enters, predicted by register and keyboard environment* — supported indirectly by the bimodality and register-gradient measurements (§5.1–§5.2), to be confirmed at the individual level by the planned survey. - *A foreign gate is mandatory* — confirmed by direct measurement (§7: 166→0 corruptions in the wild). - *Coverage, not context, is the recall bottleneck; a static prior plus a lexicon suffices at runtime* — confirmed by the coverage curve and the left-vs-right result (§8.3, §9). Wording throughout is deliberately conservative: claims are framed as “we provide evidence that...” rather than “we prove...”, and “an LLM is unnecessary for the measured residual” rather than “no LLM is ever needed”.

Planned human-subjects validation (not yet run). The one piece of evidence the corpus work cannot supply is the writer's own account of *why* and *when* they shave. A short diaspora survey is planned (≈14 questions, ~3 minutes, five blocks: keyboard layout and devices; formal vs. informal writing mode and the reasons for switching; awareness of shaving; autocorrect and backspace-correction behaviour; demographics including language variety, Montenegrin included). It is designed with a neutral tone (shaving is never called an “error”), informed-consent and no email collection, distributed on neutral Serbo-Croatian-Latin channels. This is recorded here as planned methodology, transparently distinguished from the completed corpus results above.

12. Reproducibility

All reported numbers live in a machine-readable `results_aggregate.tsv`.

```
# Confidence interval for any cell (document-level cluster bootstrap):
recall_ci.py --code sr --corpus <doc.jsonl> [--no-resolve] [--seed 12345]

# Real-error track (fetches SentiComments.SR on demand):
eval_senticomments.py --code sr [--no-resolve]
```

```

# Baselines (do-nothing, most-frequent):
baselines.py --code sr --corpus <doc.jsonl>

# Full dictionary rebuild:
filter_hunspell.py → build_deshishana.py → build_resolve_table.py → inject_resolve.py

# Register × language matrix:
build_corpus_matrix.py
for c in sr hr bs; do for g in wiki news tatoeba; do
  recall_ci.py --code $c --no-resolve --corpus cell_${c}_${g}.jsonl --label $c-$g
done; done

```

Wiki/news cells use Leipzig sentences (Serbian transliterated to Latin via `cyr2lat_sr`); Tatoeba dumps provide clean sentences (CC-BY). Raw corpora are not committed (size + terms of service); reproducibility runs through the scripts plus the seeded bootstrap plus the aggregate TSV. The supporting tool set includes `build_deshishana.py`, `build_resolve_table.py/build_resolve_any.py`, `inject_resolve.py`, `filter_hunspell.py`, `filter_leipzig.py`, `cyr2lat_sr.py`, `eval_deshishana.py`, `ablate_deshishana.py`, `recall_ci.py`, `baselines.py`, `eval_senticomments.py`, `build_corpus_matrix.py`, and `test_montenegrin_szz.py`.

Code and data availability. All repository references in this document are pinned to an immutable commit, so they remain valid even if files are later renamed or restructured. The numbers above were read from ioDiacritics commit `be745a653605f6934ea127f1c2c909e242055b5d` (main, 2026-06-13); the permalink is <https://github.com/ilya000/ioDiacritics/tree/be745a653605f6934ea127f1c2c909e242055b5d>. Relative to that commit: the engine (Swift core + C++17 port), the build/evaluation tool set (tools/), the per-experiment reports and corpus-matrix notes (research/), the paper-facing snapshot (RESEARCH.md), and the data-licensing audit (docs/DATA_LICENSE_AUDIT.md); the package is MIT. Runnable SwiftUI (macOS) and C++ Dear ImGui (Windows/macOS/Linux) demos are in ioDiacritics-Demos at commit `bf392d353fe33fc1913cf5eea613886ed4bd0cdf` (<https://github.com/ilya000/ioDiacritics-Demos/tree/bf392d353fe33fc1913cf5eea613886ed4bd0cdf>). For a citable identifier, this exact state will additionally be archived as a tagged release on Zenodo, DOI [10.5281/zenodo.20688771](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20688771). SlipWay derives from DrPaste (<https://github.com/ilya000/DrPaste>).

13. Data provenance and licenses

The ioDiacritics engine code is MIT. The bundled dictionaries are **generated artifacts from mixed third-party sources** and are not “MIT-only data”; provenance is documented separately, and a clean-MIT release can ship code and tools without the bundled dictionaries.

Source	License	Role
Serbian curated word list (turanjanin/serbian-language-tools)	MIT	sr lexicon provenance
redi (clarinsi/redi)	Apache-2.0	prior-art restoration system (hr/sr/sl)
FrequencyWords / OpenSubtitles (hermitdave)	code MIT / content CC BY-SA 4.0	hr/bs frequency lists
Leipzig Wortschatz corpora	CC BY	independent prior for resolve + validation
Tatoeba	CC BY 2.0	clean validation sentences (hrv/bos)
Hunspell hr/sr (LibreOffice)	LGPL / SISSL	lexicon filter
SETimes.SR	—	news gold eval

Source	License	Role
SentiComments.SR	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	real-error gold (NonCommercial)

Practical posture for release: a LICENSE (MIT) for code, a NOTICE file documenting the separate data provenance, and — where a clean-MIT artifact is needed — code and tools published without the bundled dictionaries, since the numbers are reproducible from scripts plus a seeded bootstrap.

14. Related work

- **Ivković (2013, 2015)** — existence and ideology of shaved text; 71% / 56.5% de-diacritization on two news sites; a technology-driven explanation.
- **Šantić, Šnajder, Bašić (2009)** — Croatian: dictionary-only 97%, + bigram LM 98.81%.
- **Ljubešić, Erjavec, Fišer (2016)** — corpus-based diacritic restoration for South Slavic; 99.5% standard / 99.2% non-standard; the *redi* tool.
- **Krstev, Stanković, Vitas (2018)** — knowledge- and rule-based restoration in Serbian; precision 98.93%, recall 94.94%; treatment of *reci/reči/reći* and frequency thresholds.
- **Batanović, Cvetanović, Nikolić (2020)** — SentiComments.SR (PLoS ONE), used here as the real-error gold set; a BiLSTM approach for Serbian is also reported in this line of work.
- **Magner (2001), Hentschel (1998)** — “Internet Slavic”; diacritic loss noted. The **Janes / ReLDI** programme — technical/linguistic standardness annotation and corpora.

What is new here: a single-method quantification across 8 registers; decontamination of frequency priors; documented bimodality; the δ effect; orthogonality to manual standardness; a decade-later replication of Ivković; an open task inventory; decomposition of the residual (0.49%; 13/397 forms); the structural impossibility on code-switching with a wild-data confirmation; *error-mass* \neq *traffic-mass*; *prior beats small bigram*; *left-only sufficiency*; the research \leftrightarrow implementation loop; and the symmetric matrix showing the cross-language gap is coverage, not language.

All numbers were produced by scripts on open data and cross-checked against the aggregate results table; the raw resolution tables are summarized rather than reproduced and remain regenerable from the documented pipeline.